

CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITES SANDWICH RAMP FAILURE UNDER TENSILE LOADING

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SUMMARY

In composite sandwich structures, the ramp down from sandwich to solid laminate is a weak point. To investigate their failure, sandwich ramp specimens were tested in tension. Failure loads were lower with core ramp reinforcing manufacturing scenarios such as wrapped glass fabric, unidirectional noodle, potty or foam. Failure load was also lower for smaller ramp radius, highlighting the importance of manufacturing control.

Keywords: sandwich ramp, failure analysis, automated fibre placement, modelling

INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures are commonly used to obtain an optimal weight while achieving the desired part strength and bending stiffness. In such structures, the sandwich construction is typically ramped down to monolithic laminates in some areas, for example at the part edges to protect the core from environment exposure, or in areas where a highly loaded joint exists. Because the distance between the facesheets varies through the ramp area, in-plane loads induce a bending moment, as shown in the freebody diagram on Figure 1 [1].

Figure 1 Freebody diagram of a sandwich rampdown (from [1])

Flatwise tensile stresses in the taper tip radius results from the change in direction of the ramped facesheet load. Experience has shown that this is indeed the area where failure is likely to occur in such structures.

In reference [2], tapered composite structures with varying taper angle and core thicknesses were tested in tension, compression and bending; the material was AS4/3501-6 and the facesheets were unidirectional. It was found that:

- In tension, initial damage originated at the root of the taper; for thinner core, delamination propagated into the core and solid laminate simultaneously while for thicker core, delamination propagated in the solid laminate first followed by propagation in the core.
- In tension, more load was transferred from flat facesheet to ramped facesheet as the core thickness decreased.
- In tension, the initial failure load had a stronger dependence on core thickness than taper angle; for a higher taper angle, the initial failure load decreased.
- In bending, the flat facesheet debonded from the core; failure load was the same with bending load applied in one direction or the other.
- In compression, the damage also initiated at the root of the taper, between the core and the flat facesheet and the flat facesheet buckled.

The present study focuses on the effect of ramp radius at the tip of the core and the effect of core tip manufacturing scenarios in sandwich tapered specimens under static tensile loading.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The specimen configuration is shown in Figure 2. The core thickness and the specimen width are 25.4 mm (1"). Potty is used in the gripping area to provide compressive strength.

The material used for the facesheet was 5276-1/T40-800 and the film adhesive was FM300-2M-06PSF. The core material was Kevlar N636, with a cell size of 3.2 mm (0.125") and a density of 72 kg/m³. The potting compound was Loctite EA9306NA. The foam was Rohacell 110 WF.

Figure 2 Specimen geometry

As shown in Table 1, the effect of the taper tip radius was studied using four tool radius and five taper configurations were used to investigate the effect of core tip manufacturing.

Table 1 Summary of the test parameters.

Tool radius R (mm)	Taper Configuration	Set	Number
9.7	none	1	3
16.0	none		3
25.4	none		3
38.1	none		3
9.7	fiberglass		3
	noodle	3	
	potty	3	
	foam	3	
	none (core splicing and chamfering)	2	12

As shown in Figure 3, the five different configurations used in the tapered area were: no material added, a thin glass fabric wrapping the honeycomb tip, a thin glass fabric wrapping a unidirectional noodle, potty at the taper root, foam in the tapered area.

The assumptions were that the glass fabric might prevent the delamination from growing into the solid laminate side by preventing damage initiation and that the unidirectional noodle, potty or foam might increase flatwise strength. For the purpose of comparison, all taper configurations were manufactured using the tool radius of 9.7 mm.

Figure 3 Taper configurations

To experiment with core splicing and core positioning options, additional specimens were made using the tool radius of 9.7 and no taper configuration. The only differences

were splicing of the core in the constant core thickness area and a 10° chamfer at the top of the ramp, to help position the core and conform it to the cavity. Since these differences were away from the critical taper tip area, they should not influence failure and these specimens were used here to provide additional data points. A total of 36 specimens were manufactured in two groups a few weeks apart.

Specimen Manufacturing

The specimens were manufactured at the National Research Council of Canada laboratory, using the Automated Fibre Placement (AFP) process. To simulate the process that occurs on a realistic part, the fibre placement tool corresponds to the ramped side. In order to investigate the effect of the taper tip radius, the tool was composed of four sections with the different taper tip radius indicated in Table 1.

The first facesheet was deposited on this convex surface (see Figure 4). Then the film adhesive layer was installed followed by the honeycomb core pieces and by another layer of adhesive. The adhesive layers overshot the core tip by about 6.4 mm (0.25"). Finally, the second facesheet was fibre placed as a flat surface.

The part was then removed from the AFP tool, flipped and placed on a flat plate for curing, flat facesheet against the tool. No top plate or pressure intensifier were used. The parts were cured using standard autoclave procedure with a 207 kPa pressure. After curing, three specimens were cut from each panel.

Figure 4 Ramped facesheet (left) and flat facesheet (right) being placed on the tool using Automated Fiber Placement

Experimental Procedure

Prior to testing, a photograph of the specimen edge was taken at each of the ramp radius on each side of the specimen. The photograph included a graduated ruler.

The radius at the taper root was measured using image analysis of the photograph. Using the software Image Tool, the photograph was calibrated, points were picked on the radius outer edge and the coordinates (x,y) were calculated. The radius was estimated using a “fit circle” algorithm implemented in Matlab. The algorithm best fits a

circle through the measured points by the method of least squares with minimized geometric errors [3] and outputs an estimated radius.

All specimens were tested on a hydraulic test machine in tension. The specimens were clamped using hydraulic grips with emery paper to prevent slippage. An optimal grip oil pressure of 6.9 MPa (42.3 kN equivalent load) was used to avoid both slippage and crushing in the grip area. The stroke rate was 1.15 mm/min and the data acquisition rate was 1 Hz.

TEST RESULTS

The tensile test failure mode was similar for all specimens. Failure was sudden and catastrophic. The strain gauge output for one specimen instrumented with 6 strain gauges is shown in Figure 5. The slight nonlinearity resulting from the specimen eccentricity can be seen clearly. This agrees with the noticeable bending seen in the specimen during the test. We can also notice that in the solid laminate area, the strains are almost the same on both facesheets, while in the core area, they are higher in the flat facesheet than in the ramped one. Moreover, although the strain gauges in the ramp area were close to the taper tip, the strains are close in magnitude to the strains in the constant core area, indicating a sudden change in the facesheet strains at the taper tip.

Figure 5 Strain Gauge output

A photograph of a failed specimen (no taper configuration) is shown in Figure 6 (a), while a schematic illustrates the failure pattern in Figure 6 (b). The initiation site was confirmed by monitoring the taper tip areas on one specimen loaded under fatigue cycling, where the damage progression is stable and slow.

Failure initiated at the very tip of the honeycomb taper, by matrix cracks in the 90° and 45° layers, which grew as a delamination between the 45° and 0° degree layer towards the monolithic section (delamination A), and simultaneously as a delamination between

the 90° and 0° degree layer towards sandwich section (delamination B). The delamination between the 90° and 0° layers then grew back through the 90° layer and continues in the honeycomb, following the honeycomb/facesheet interface (delamination C). The transition from delamination B to C tends to occur at the end of the resin pocket which is created at the tip of the taper by the adhesive flowing in the honeycomb.

It is possible that the orientation of the 90° layer which is the first ply against the core in the ramped facesheet promotes the initiation of failure due to the low resistance of a tape lamina to transverse cracking. It would be interesting to verify if changing this ply orientation to a 45° or 0° would result in higher failure loads

Figure 6 Failed area (a) and failure pattern (b), no taper configuration

As shown in Figure 7, the various taper configurations tested had a failure pattern very similar to the above. There was only slight variation in the position and length of delamination B, where delamination B can be between the honeycomb and the 90 layer, or delamination B can be shorter. Also, for the noodle configuration, the delamination went around the noodle completely.

Figure 7 Taper configurations failure patterns

Effect of Taper Configuration

A summary of the mean failure loads and coefficients of variation is shown in Figure 8 for the five taper configurations. The highest failure load obtained was for the first scenario, no material added at the taper root.

Figure 8 Effect of taper configurations

The glass fabric wrapping the honeycomb tip reduced the failure load by 4%, while the potty reduces it by 15%. Finally, the glass fabric wrapping a unidirectional was the most detrimental with a 25% reduction as well as the foam. Therefore the attempts to reinforce the sandwich ramp taper root area were not conclusive. More work is needed to understand the causes of these lower failure loads: they could be due to poor adhesion with the added materials as evidenced by the change in location of delamination B; they could also be due to higher stress concentrations resulting from change in stiffness right at the taper tip. A better understanding of these mechanisms is necessary to devise stronger sandwich ramp down manufacturing scenarios.

Effect of Taper Tip Radius

When only the tool radius was varied (no taper configuration), the measured radius did not exactly reflect the tool radius: the resulting radius was bigger than the tool radius for R of 9.7 mm and 16.0 mm and smaller than tool radius for larger R. This is not surprising as the panels were cured with the ramped facesheet on the bagside. The radius effect on failure load was not very pronounced as can be seen with the solid blue lozenges on Figure 9. All remaining specimens were manufactured on a tool radius of 9.7 mm and as can be seen on Figure 9, the taper configurations (empty symbols) have resulting radii smaller than the previous ones. It was observed, in particular for the noodle case, that the radius was not smooth, probably because the noodle did not compact uniformly. This resulted in a localized depression of smaller radius. This fact might have contributed to the lower failure loads.

Figure 9 Effect of ramp radius on failure load

The two groups of specimens manufactured at several weeks interval resulted in very different radii. The first set of specimens had bigger radii than the second, as can be

seen on Figure 9 (blue versus pink symbols). For both sets of specimens, the materials and layup were identical. As can be seen from the inset photograph and from the radius measurements, the first set of specimen which had higher failure load also had bigger radius, which establishes a relation between taper tip radius and failure load. It is believed that bevels around the second set of panels were omitted, resulting in core shifting and smaller radius. If this was the case, it shows how crucial it is to prevent core shifting during manufacturing in order to maximize the strength of the structure. Another possible explanation is that chamfering the core at the top of the ramp resulted in a different positioning of the core. For the earlier specimens that were not chamfered, the core would not sit tight against the 20° tool ramp, therefore there might have been more gap between the core tip and the radius. In either case, it seems the positioning of the core has an important effect.

CONCLUSIONS

The effect of ramp radius at the tip of the core and the effect of core tip manufacturing scenarios in sandwich tapered specimens under static tensile loading were studied.

The failure pattern was identified. Since failure initiated in the 90° first ply against the core in the ramped facesheet, it might be possible to increase failure loads by changing the orientation of this first ply.

Several manufacturing scenarios were used at the taper tip with the goal of increasing the strength of sandwich ramp down, but they resulted in lower failure loads.

Specimens which exhibited smaller taper tip radii resulted in noticeably lower failure loads. Core shifting during cure or core positioning in the tool cavity might be possible causes, which emphasizes the importance of core positioning in the manufacturing of parts.

Correlation of the results with a 3D solid finite element model is underway to examine the stress distribution in the failure area. The fundamental understanding of failure in the sandwich ramp area will help in designing more resistant structures.

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